
A STUDY ON EFFECT OF WORKING ENVIRONMENT ON EMPLOYEES PRODUCTIVITY OF ARECA LEAF BIO PLATES VITTAL

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ABSTRACT:

A workplace is a place where someone goes to work, either for their employer or for themselves. The effectiveness of the workforce has a significant impact on the organization's success. The simple concept underpinning the movement for better working environment is that comfortable workers are more productive. Businesses now understand how critical it is to boost productivity, retain great employees, and keep a competitive edge by fostering a comfortable work environment.

Eco-Bliss is an India's leading Areca leaf plates exporter and manufacturer locating in Balipaguli of Vittal. They offer a gilt free dining solution with its eco-friendly range is cutlery, plates, and bowls of superior quality. It is the first Areca Leaf plates manufacturing and exporting company of India. This research paper can throw some light into the effect of working environment on employees productivity with special reference to the eco-bliss manufacturer and exporter of areca leaf bio plates.

KEYWORDS:

Working environment, employees productivity, leaf plates manufacturing and exporting.

Introduction

A workplace is a place where someone goes to work, either for their employer or for themselves. The effectiveness of the workforce has a significant impact on the organization's success. When an employee's productivity even slightly changes, it can have a significant effect.

The simple concept underpinning the movement for better working environment is that comfortable workers are more productive. Businesses now understand how critical it is to boost productivity, retain great employees, and keep a competitive edge by fostering a comfortable work environment. The working environment's contribution to reaching organizational goals must be sufficient.

Eco-Bliss is an India's leading Areca leaf plates exporter and manufacturer locating in Balipaguli of Vittal. They offer a guilt free dining solution with its eco-friendly range is cutlery, plates, and bowls of superior quality. It is the first Areca Leaf plates manufacturing and exporting company of India. It has led a model of sustainable kitchenware in the global market.

The symbiotic relationship with the local farmers has ensured mutual growth while serving Mother Earth. Given the environmental toll, avoiding products that generate Green House Gases isn't a choice anymore and need to be the way of life. They use machines for producing the buff plates. The cost of one machine is rupees 15000. These machines were developed by the proprietor Mr. Rajaram Bhatt whose qualification is Mechanical Engineer. Training programs given to the newly appointed employees with salary, and after that they become permanent employee of the company. More than 80% workers are women in the company.

1.1 Need for the study:

- » The study is very much needed to understand the relationship between working environment and employee productivity.
- » To know employees expectations in the workplace.

- » To prove the necessity of motivational factors in the work-place.

1.2 Objectives of the study:

- » To analyze the effect of working environment on employees productivity.
- » To know the use of job aids towards employees productivity.
- » To study the effect of working environment on the morale and interpersonal relationships among the employees.
- » To examine whether supervisor support contribute towards employees' performance.

1.3 Hypothesis:

H0: The work environmental factors does not have significant influence on productivity of employees.

H1: The work environmental factors have significant influence on productivity of employees.

1.4 Research methodology:

1.4.1 Research Design:

This study adopted a descriptive type of research approach for analyzing the effect of work environment on productivity of the employees of Eco-Bliss areca leaf bio-plates factory Vittal.

Method of data collection:

1. **Primary data:** For this study the data was collected from primary data through telephone interview.
2. **Secondary data:** For this study, the secondary data was collected through internet and text books.

For this study, sample of 30 respondents were considered from the population.

For this study, random sampling technique was followed.

The analysis of data has done by using statistical technique percentage method.

1.5 Scope of the study:

The study has conducted on the specific company i.e., Eco-Bliss Areca Leaf plates exporter Vittal. The main intention to conduct this study is to find out the effect of good working environment on employees productivity. Employees' productivity matters a lot for the success of an organization. The behavior of an employee depends on the working environment provided to him at the work-place.

Limitations:

- » The study has conducted within limited time period.
- » The sample size is only 30, which may not sufficient for the total population.
- » The study is only confined to Eco-Bliss Bio plates Manufacturer and Exporter.
- » The suggestions and recommendations are given based on the data available.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

Part 1: It includes the demographic profile of the respondents like age, gender, qualification, marital status income level, designation, and work experience.

Table 2.1: Age of the respondents

Age of the respondents	Number of respondents	In percentage (%)
20-30	3	10
30-40	9	30
40-50	16	53
Above 50	2	7
Total	30	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows that among 30 respondents, 10% respondents are within the age group of 20-30 years, 30% respondents are within the age group of 30-40 years, 53% respondents are belongs to the age group of 40-50 years, And only 7% respondents are belongs to the age group of above 50 years.

Table 2.2: Gender of the respondents

Gender	Number of respondents	In percentage (%)
Male	4	13
Female	26	87
Total	30	100

Interpretation:

The above table and pie chart depicts that, among total 30 respondents, only 13% respondents are Male and rest 87% respondents are female.

Table 2.3: Qualification of the respondents

Qualification	Number of respondents	In percentage (%)
Primary	13	44
High school	12	40
PUC	3	10
Graduation	1	3
Post-graduation	0	0
Others	1	3
Total	30	100

Interpretation:

The above table and pie chart reveals that among total respondents, The education qualification of 44% respondents were Prima-

ry, and of 40% respondents were high school, and 10% respondents are of PUC and only 3% respondents was an graduated.

Table 2.4: Work experience of the respondents

Work Experience	Number of respondents	In percentage (%)
Less than 1 year	5	16
2- 5 years	5	17
5 - 10 years	15	50
More than 10 years	5	17
Total	30	100

Interpretation:

It is understood from the above table and pie chart that, 16% respondents are having less than 1 year work experience, and 17% respondents are having 2-5 years of work experience, and 50% respondents are having 5-10 years of work experience, and remaining 17% are having more than 10 years of work experience.

Part 2: It contains the interpretation of data collected from the survey other than demographic information.

Table 2.5: Opinion of the respondents about the statement “My workplace is provided with efficient lighting”.

Particulars	Number of respondents	In percentage (%)
Strongly agree	30	100
Agree	0	0
Neutral	0	0
Disagree	0	0
Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	30	100

Interpretation:

The above table and bar chart describes that, 100% respondents strongly agreed for the above statement.

Table 2.6: Opinion of respondents about the statement “Number of windows in my work area complete my fresh air and light need”.

Particulars	Number of respondents	In percentage (%)
Strongly agree	28	93
Agree	2	7
Neutral	0	0
Disagree	0	0
Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	30	100

Interpretation:

The above table and bar chart exhibits that, among 30 respondents, 93% respondents strongly agreed for the statement and only 7% respondents just agreed the above statement.

Table 2.7: Data about different health issues facing by the employees.

Particulars	Number of respondents	In percentage (%)
Headache	2	40
Back pain	0	0
Nerve problem	0	0
Eye side problem	1	20
BP	0	0
Carpal tunnel syndrome	0	0
Any other: Allergy	2	40

Particulars	Number of respondents	In percentage (%)
None of the above	0	0

Interpretation:

The above table and bar chart describes that, Among 4 respondents (who face health issues), 40% respondents were facing headache, 20% respondents were facing eye side problem and another 40% respondents were facing allergy problems due to their job.

Table 2.8: Data about the other problems faced by the employees.

Particulars	Number of respondents	In percentage (%)
Yes	1	3
No	29	97
Total	30	100

Interpretation:

The above table and pie chart exhibits that, among total 30 respondents, 3% of the respondents faced some problem other than health issues, and the rest 97% never faced any problems.

FINDINGS:

It is found that, majority of the respondents were belongs to the age group of 40- 50 and only 10% of the respondents were belongs to the age group of 20-30.

From the study, it is found that majority of the respondents were female and only 13% of the respondents were male.

Among 30 respondents, majority of the respondents were primary educated; only few respondents were studied PUC.

It is found that, majority of the respondents were married and only few are unmarried.

From the study, majority of the respondents were having 5-10 years of work experience and 50% of the remaining respondents were having more than 10 years of work experience.

From the study, it is found that 100% of the respondents strongly agreed for efficient lighting facility provided at the workplace.

It is found from the study that, 93% of the respondents were strongly agreed. Majority of the respondents were said that, the workplace is provided with well-ventilated window facility to complete fresh air and light needs.

Among those respondents who face health issues, it is found that, 50% of the respondents face headache and only few respondents face eye side problem. Majority of the respondents face headache problem by their job.

100% of the respondents were did not face any problems at their workplace.

SUGGESTIONS:

- » Employees' performance matters a lot for the success of an organization. So, the company should communicate its goals or objectives and strategies with their employees, so that they can work effectively to achieve those goals.
- » Promotion and Recognition is also one of the factors which motivate employees to work with fuller potential. So, the company can recognize employees' achievements in their work and give promotion.
- » Employees are highly satisfied with the working environment provided at the company. So the company should maintain consistency in maintaining work environment, so that labour turnover can be reduced.

CONCLUSION:

Working environment is one of the most important compo-

nents which influence employee performance within an organizational setting. In today's competitive world, only monetary benefits are not enough for employees in order to achieve higher performance levels. Eco-Bliss is one of the company which created employment opportunities for the rural people. It is found that most of the respondents have shared positive opinion about the working environment provided at the workplace. And also majority of the respondents were highly satisfied with the work environmental factors at the workplace. So, the organization must maintain consistency in creating good working environment so that the employees can work more effectively in achieving organizational goals.

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